

VIRTUAL TESTING METHODOLOGY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF ADVANCED LIGHTWEIGHT DEBRIS CONTAINMENT SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Developing design methodologies based on experimentally validated predictive numerical simulation methods will enhance existing capabilities in predicting failure modes and structural design optimization for the high velocity impact problems. This paper is thus concerned with the setup of a virtual testing methodology for the development of advanced lightweight debris containment system with application to the case of a real hybrid metallic/soft layered composite fan case structure. To realize this new design, a debris protection fan case composed of a basic metallic shell structure with a dry Kevlar wrap around it is considered. The fan blade is made of titanium alloy modeled by a Johnson-Cook elastoplastic material in ABAQUS code, while the metallic structure of the fan case is made of aluminum alloy also modeled as an elastoplastic material. A multilayered Kevlar *woven dry fabric* structure is wrapped around the thin aluminum shell to form a soft hybrid fan case. A mesoscale woven fabric material model developed in ABAQUS has been used. This material model can capture the ballistic response of multi-layer fabric panels and is implemented as a VUMAT subroutine in an equivalent smeared shell element corresponding to the representative volume element (RVE) for computational efficiency. The aim here is to assess how this material model can be applied in a real industrial application and successful numerical simulation shows that it is possible to predict both for plate and curved shell structure the number of layers required to ensure containment.

1. INTRODUCTION

The numerical simulations of perforation and penetration of targets by projectiles are subjects of interest since the 1970's. One such interesting application is the design and analysis of efficient lightweight engine fan blade out containment system [2,10,14]. In fact, in case of such engine malfunction, engine debris poses a serious threat to aircrafts and their occupants. For protecting aircrafts and their passengers, conventional methods rely on the use of heavy structures to restrict debris from escaping the containment case. However for better energy and economy efficiency, the need to strengthen and lighten aircrafts without sacrificing on improved safety requirements has pushed the aerospace industry to explore alternatives to existing metallic containment systems [7,10]. Such alternatives are made of either soft wall (i.e. a hybrid metallic/soft layered composite fan case) [1, 2] or of hard wall (i.e. hard woven reinforced layered composite casing). Hybrid fan case containment structure considered here is a novel design in the aerospace industry which combines the resistance of the metallic structures with the lightness and energy absorption capability of the composite structures.

Developing design methodologies based on experimentally validated predictive numerical simulation methods will thus enhance existing capabilities in predicting failure modes and structural design optimization for the high velocity impact problems [1,3].

The aim of this paper is to propose a modeling and simulation methodology for use in virtual testing approach for the design of a real lightweight containment structure. This paper thus proposes a modeling methodology for the simulation of the containment problem for the case of realistic The debris protection casing is a hybrid metallic/soft layered composite structure, composed of a basic metallic shell layer, made

of aluminum, around which woven Kevlar dry fabric layers are wrapped. The fan blade is made of titanium. Both metallic parts use standard plasticity coupled with damage models available in ABAQUS. The dry Kevlar fabric wrap is modeled by a computationally efficient shell-based mesoscale mechanics unit-cell model, suitable for ballistic impact response of multi-layer fabric laminates and implemented in ABAQUS software via its VUMAT facility [9].

In order to simulate the impact between the blade debris and the hybrid fan case, a multistep analysis process is used. In the first step, one performs a preloading stage using an implicit analysis to generate stress and strain in the blades as well as the global velocity vector of the blade induced by the build-up of the cruise rotational velocity. In the second step one performs an explicit analysis to study the impact between the blade debris and the hybrid fan case using results from the previous step. Some of the main issues considered in assessing the suitability of a computational model in industrial environment include finding a constitutive law capable of capturing the complex physical interaction including intra and inter layers failure mechanisms as well as contact interactions related to the gap size between the adjacent layers, and finding the appropriate mesh size limited by available computer capacity and production time [11,12]. A parametric study is then performed for assessing how this material model can be applied to an industrial problem and to further evaluate if our predictions in terms of the number of plies needed to contain the debris and total weight reduction are in agreement with industry observations.

The analysis comprises two separate sub-models: (i) a pre-stress model for initialization of field variables induced by setting up the motion of the fan blade from rest to cruise rotating speed; (ii) the model for blade debris release and its impact with the engine casing. The modeling technique is thus interesting in the sense that we use a first model to pre-constrain the fan blade following the rotating motion built-up and then use the accumulated deformation history to start the subsequent impact analysis. The setup of these two models is dealt with using specific tools and functionalities of ABAQUS software. The first analysis is solely concerned with the fan blade and is used to obtain the initial stresses and strains appearing in each element as well as the velocities of each node of the fan blade model when it is put in rotational motion. In ABAQUS, this motion is defined by specifying an axis of rotation and a rotational velocity as well as multipoint constraints (MPCs). This analysis step is performed using ABAQUS implicit solver, i.e. ABAQUS standard. The results of this analysis are then

imported in the subsequent analysis which deals with the impact of the fan blade debris on the engine casing. In this second analysis phase, a new part, called engine casing, is created and assembled with the previous fan blade model. A hybrid engine casing is modeled using an aluminum cylindrical shell as the base structure defining the casing shape around which a dry fabric composite material is wrapped. For high velocity impact modeling involved in this containment simulation, the ABAQUS explicit solver is used together with the developed VUMAT [9].

2. DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF BALLISTIC FABRIC MODEL

In this paper, a simplified engine fan blade containment problem is considered as an application of the work presented in ref [3]. Figure 1 show the modelling simplification process where one reduce a full fan blade casing to a representative five blade casing:(fig1.1) initial real metallic fan-blade with casing;(fig 1.2) simplified real system without hub reduced to 5 blades and casing ,and (fig 1.3): simplified five blade pre-stress results

Figure 1. Model simplification process

The objective is to replace the existing metallic fan case of figure 1 by a lighter hybrid composite fan case and the problem is to determine how many fabric layers are required to contain a fan debris in case of fan-blade-out event. A section of the simplified real hybrid metal/composite fan case is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2 Section of simplified hybrid aluminium /Kevlar fabric of real fan-case

The debris protection case is composed of a basic metallic shell layer, made of aluminum, around which woven Kevlar dry fabric layers are wrapped and the fan blade is made of titanium. Both metallic parts use standard plasticity coupled with damage models available in ABAQUS or LSDYNA. All parameters and model geometry used in the paper are taken from our previous work [3,8] done using Ls-Dyna environment[1] in order to validate our modeling results in ABAQUS environment.

The dry Kevlar fabric wrap is modeled by an efficient shell element-based meso-scale mechanics unit-cell model, corresponding to the RVE that is suitable for ballistic impact response of multi-layer fabric laminates and implemented in ABAQUS software via its VUMAT facility or in Lsdyna via its UMAT facility. In order to enhance our existing capabilities in predicting failure modes and structural design optimization for the high velocity impact problems, our design methodologies is being developed based on experimentally validated predictive numerical simulation methods. Figure 3 shows a comparison between the predicted and the ELVS measured velocity-time history for four-ply of fully fixed Kevlar® 129 fabric panel impacted on its centre by a blunt-nosed projectile with a striking velocity of 120m/s for a selected mesh size.

Figure 3a): projectile-fabric plate assembly; 3b): Mesh size influence over the analysis results; 3c) Comparison between FEM and experimental analyses of the impact velocity [see 3 for details]

3. METHODOLOGY FOR THE NUMERICAL SIMULATION OF A FAN BLADE CONTAINMENT PROBLEM

Once validated, the developed soft fabric constitutive model is then used to conduct an industrial-like simulation. Figure 6 illustrates the virtual spin testing model.

Multistep analysis methodology: The impact between the blade and the hybrid fan case was simulated using a multistep analysis process. In the **first step**, one performs a preloading stage using a dynamic implicit analysis to generate stress and strain in the blades as well as the global velocity vector of the blade, induced by the build-up of the cruise rotational velocity from zero initial velocity to 1047rad/s. The **second step** then performs an explicit analysis for debris generation and for studying the impact between the blade debris and the hybrid fan case using results from the previous step. Here a multilayer dry Kevlar fabric wrapped around the metallic fan case is modeled using a mesoscale Fabric Crossover material model developed either as Abaqus VUMAT or as Lsdyna UMAT model [2, 3].

Implicit analysis: Stress Induced in the Blades by the Rotation

This pre-stress analysis was performed using the ABAQUS Standard implicit solver for transient dynamic structural problems involving high velocity loadings. The model data generation involved the creation of the blades geometry and the assignment of material properties to the parts.

To simplify the problem, an overall simplified geometry of the fan blade similar to the one used in [1, 3] is adopted. However, instead of using a four blades model as in the above references, only one blade is used here as in spin-test. Moreover, it was found more appropriate for ABAQUS to use a blade with curved outer edge line in order to obtain good convergence of the contact algorithm and to avoid high stress and strain concentration at one of the sharp outer edges of the blade and to reduce the computational time.

Defining the geometry and the material of the fan blade: In order to introduce a crack in the second analysis step, the fan blade is modeled using two distinct features or parts and this is done where the fan blade is broken into two parts (Figure 4): one that remains attached to the rotating shaft and the other that is ejected outward as a debris that impact the casing.

Figure 4: Two features fan blade geometric profile defined in ABAQUS

The thickness of the blade shell elements is 4.98 mm and the material properties input in ABAQUS are the same as those used in Ls-Dyna by [3] to model the behaviour of the blade.

Constraining the model and boundary conditions: Two kinds of coupling are used in ABAQUS, in order to perform a flexible multibody analysis for rotating parts, First, one **attach the base of the blade to the control point** at which the rotational motion boundary conditions are applied (Figure 5a) and then the two parts of the fan blade are attached by using the **tie constraint** (as it is able to rigidly connect two sets of nodes very close to each other). Finally, in order to transmit the radial velocity applied to the reference point to the fan blade, one has to define a **kinematic coupling constraint** between the reference point and the nodes at the base of the blade where the junction between the blade and the rotating shaft is located. The junction between the two parts is shown in Figure b.

Figure 5: a) Coupling constraint between the control point and the base of the fan blade. b) Tie constraint between the two sub-components of the fan blade.

Velocity boundary conditions: As discussed in [], a velocity boundary condition was applied to the reference point in a very **smooth manner using of the amplitude function**. The progressive application of the rotating motion up to an the angular radial velocity to 1047 rad/s ensure that no any element distort nor any unnecessary strain or stress are created on the fan blade structure during the first seconds of the motion. Figure 6 gives the shape of the used amplitude corresponding to a smooth step time. It was noted that non-smooth step time amplitude could result in infinite acceleration of the blade base nodes that distort the mesh and cause the analysis to crash. This **smooth step time has been applied over 9 seconds** meaning that the engine rotating speed goes from 0 to 1047 rad/s in that period of time.

Hence the **velocities that are fed to the next analysis phase are extracted at time** equal to 9 seconds as it is marked by a red dot in Figure . The velocity vector at each node of the fan blade is then exported to the second analysis and this information enable one to apply a velocity boundary condition in the impact analysis that will set the blade in motion in the explicit analysis.

Figure 6: Progressive application of the rotating motion to the fan blade

Explicit analysis: Debris Generation and Impact on the Fan Case

The objective of this analysis phase is to simulate the blade release event (generation of debris) and to model and analyze the high velocity debris impact on the fan case. The material model for the blade is the same as the one presented in ref [1]. The standard metallic engine casing is replaced by a hybrid model, meaning that it is made of an assembly of a metallic base layer and of several dry fabric composite layers wrapped around it. In the first considered model there were four layers of Kevlar fabric wrapped around the cylindrical inner aluminum shell [1,3] in order to study the effect of using plate instead of shell elements in our modeling process. Different material models are assigned to each of the two main subparts. The metallic ring structure in Aluminum (Al) is modeled with the material properties with isotropic hardening with different strain rate given in Table 1 of [1]. The Kevlar material properties are given in [3] and the Kevlar dry fabric wrap is modeled with an advanced meso-mechanical material model, the Fabric Crossover VUMAT model implemented in ABAQUS-Explicit [9]. A continuum modelling approach is used to model the fabrics in such a way that the interaction of yarns in a unit cell is smeared into a single representative ABAQUS finite strain shell element S4R. The second analysis phase is performed using the ABAQUS explicit solver. The fan blade geometry is imported from the first analysis.odb result file. Also, on that geometry a velocity predefined field calling the previous .odb result file had to be defined to set the fan blade in motion.

Defining the geometry: The first operation to set up the 2nd analysis phase is to create the geometric model of the engine casing. Then, from the implicit analysis result file, the geometry of the tip of the blade is imported and assembled to form the fan case model. In the first considered example, the engine casing is thus made of several concentric cylinders (figure 7a). The innermost cylinder is metallic and the four other cylinders are made of fabric composite materials. Of course, we will be using the developed VUMAT to model the composite behavior during impact. Each cylinder radius is increased by 0,2499 mm to account for the exact thickness of the material. The inner radius of the innermost metallic skin is 250mm; the length of the cylinder is 150 mm. These are approximately the values used in Ls-Dyna by [1, 3] which are respectively 249 mm and 105 mm.

Contact interactions, boundary conditions and predefined fields: To define the contact between the blade and each layer of material defining the casing as

well as the contact between layers themselves, a “general contact” option available in ABAQUS was used and contact properties were used to define the mechanical surface interaction models that govern the behavior of surfaces when they are in contact.

Figure 7: a) Assembly of the casing and the fan blade for the explicit analysis, b) definition of the boundary condition on the edges of the casing to fix it rigidly in space.

The default contact property model in ABAQUS /Explicit assumes “hard” contact in the normal direction. Contact property assignments propagate through all analysis steps in which the general contact interaction is active. The normal behavior is set to allow separation after contact with a “Hard” contact pressure overclosure behavior using the standard constraint enforcement method. Tangential behavior is defined to be frictionless. There is only one boundary condition applied to fix the casing in all spatial directions as shown in Figure 7b. This was applied at the two edges of the cylinders to approximate the manner in which the composite strap is integrated in the engine. The predefined fields consisting of velocities at each node of the blade as well as strains and stresses obtained at the end of the first analysis phase were extracted at the last frame, and applied to the imported geometry.

Impact results on the hybrid casing with a four fabric layers : The evolution of the blade impact analysis on the hybrid fancase is shown in the graphical results of Figure . One can notice that the blade is progressively penetrating the casing. The element deletion parameter is removing all the damaged elements from the analysis. The analysis takes approximately 20 minutes to run but this time could be reduced by modeling only half of the casing.

Figure 8: Graphical evolution of the impact analysis of the fan blade on the hybrid casing

In this configuration, the blade perforates the containment casing and exits at 125 m/s. Figure 9 shows the fan blade velocity drop during the impact. Also one notes that the second dynamic analysis is starting at the point in time where the previous analysis stopped and this is why the curve is plotted from 9.2 s. Figure 10 shows the plot of the energy curves for the internal energy (ALLIE), the kinetic energy (ALLKE) and the total energy of the model (ETOTAL) during this impact analysis.

We may observe that the total energy of the model remains constant over the duration of the analysis indicating that the model is consistent. Furthermore the observed loss of velocity is translated in a loss of kinetic energy which is transferred to the casing as internal strain energy that deforms and damages it. This is the main reason for the observed increase of internal energy of the model. Those few observations demonstrate that the model is behaving correctly.

Figure 9: Curve of the blade's velocity over the duration of the analysis

Figure 10: Energy curve of the blade's velocity over the duration of the analysis

4. Hybrid fan case containment study

Debris protection using multilayered dry fabric plate structure

In Figure 11 we show a simple study of the impact of a projectile on a plate made of increasing number of fabric layer []. This study was carried out to find out if the developed VUMAT can be used in predicting the number of fabric layers needed to prevent penetration of the blunt projectile impacting flat plate configuration. Since a shell element corresponding to the crossover model is used,

Figure 11: Influence of the number of layers over the final velocity of the projectile

the computation time needed to obtain results increases drastically with the number of layers. From these analyses on a flat multilayered plate, it is found that a configuration with 6-ply completely stopped the projectile, as shown in Figure 11.

Simplified formula to predict non-penetration

From the obtained numerical results, it was possible in [] to derive an analytic relation that could be used for prediction the numbers of layers required to prevent penetration. Figure gives a plot of such a quadratic function obtained using three simulation results and Excel interpolation/extrapolation capabilities. In equation (1) variable X is the number of layers for the case of flat plate:

$$f(X) = 2.7639X^2 - 37.161X + 118.12 \quad (1)$$

From figure 12, it can be seen that formula (1) also predicts the correct number of plies needed to stop the projectile.

Figure 12: Prediction analysis to define the number of layers needed to stop the projectile (eqn 1)

This approach will be applied in an attempt to predict the number of layers needed to prevent escape of the fan blade debris from the hybrid fan case.

Methodology for containment with a full metal casing

In a previous paper, when we tried to apply the above methodology to curved environment, we faced numerical instabilities when the number of layers exceeded 10. We then first applied it to the case of multilayered metallic structure to check if it works in case of large number of plies involving ductile isotropic layers and see if it was possible to virtually predict the number of plies required to contain the fan blade debris. Different configuration tests of the engine containment structure involving different number of 0.5 mm thick aluminum layers (actually the value used in[3] to set up the analysis in LsDyna) were used. The results are presented in table 2 and show that 24 layers are very close to stopping the projectile (figure 13) from which it was concluded that 25 layers of aluminum will definitely stop it from escaping the containment but this had to be verified a posteriori as shown in figure 14.

Figure 13: Fan containment made of 24 layers of aluminum

Number of layers	Total thickness of the casing (mm)	Final velocity of the fan blade debris (m/s)
4	2	123
8	4	111
12	6	95
18	9	82
20	10	36
24	12	0.63

Table 2: Results obtained from FEA

The result shown in Figure 14 and in table 2 was interesting since it is very close to the result obtained by [3] through the FEA model where a thickness of 12.7mm of aluminum was enough to stop the debris. Our goal in using a multilayered approach to simulate the containment feature of a metallic fancase was first to validate the adequacy of the contact algorithm used to model the interaction between numerous layers because running a multilayered fabric model resulted in severe numerical instabilities before end of simulation time when the number of fabric layers exceeded 10. Finally the FEA results were plotted in a graph to fully understand how a variation in the number of layers was affecting the final debris velocity. This is shown in figure 15 along with a quadratic regression of the results obtained through FEA modeling. An analytic expression linking the number of layers in the containment with the final velocity of the blade was also derived and is given as:

$$f(X) = -0.2643X^2 + 1.3141X + 120.41 \quad (2)$$

Figure 14: 25-layers fan containment; a) blade stopped inside the containment, b) stresses at the end of the analysis.

Figure 15: Curve of the blade's velocity over the duration of the analysis

Application to hybrid fan case

The preceding analysis for metallic structure is extended to hybrid fan case in order to find the number of fabric plies wrapped around an inner metallic casing required to contain the fan debris. As it was done before, we will correlate the number of fabric layers with the final velocity of the blade. Previous simulations for 4, 6, 8 and 10 layers of fabric were run successfully and the obtained results are presented in Figure 16 showing the final resulting velocity of the blade; but numerical instabilities were encountered when more than 10 layers were used.

Figure 16: The fan blade's velocity evolution for different configurations of the hybrid casing

Several possibilities were advocated in order to explain why simulations were crashing with more than 10 layers and these included: (i) the lack of progressive damage model in the developed VUMAT; (ii) the element deletion option in ABAQUS which remove element as soon as the damage criterion is met and this may leads to a premature loss of material implying a loss of internal energy while affecting the stability and accuracy of the contact algorithm; (ii) use of a corotational frame based on fiber frame (FF approach) to update the material stress-strain history instead of the Green-Naghdi (GN) approach used here to produce the results Badel et al[13].

Figure 17: Velocity evolution predictions of the fan blade for different configuration of the casing

From previous studies however, despite the above mentioned VUMAT deficiencies, four numerical results were used to construct an extrapolated quadratic function (Figure 17) in an effort to try to predict the number of layers required to contain the debris. One can observe that the form of the equation (eqn 3) and its coefficients are very close to the one obtained for the fully metallic casing (eqn 2). It is not surprising that adding layers to the containment affects the final velocity of the debris in the similar way.

The interpolation/extrapolation performed in Excel using the FEA results yields the following function to predict the number of Kevlar layers needed to stop the blade:

$$f(x) = -0.2131x^2 + 1.5999x + 129.97 \quad (3)$$

In its turn, this analytic function was used to compute some predictions of the residual velocity in terms of number of fabric plies. The results are shown in red in Figure 17. According to this preliminary analysis one could conclude that approximately 30 layers of fabric are needed to stop the projectile from completely perforating the engine casing. Hence, in order to further support this conclusion we had to run a very large analysis with a 30 layers of fabric configuration of the containment vessel.

And this was possible made possible with the new Abaqus 6.12 version. A deeper investigation of the reason why the simulations were crashing beyond 10 layers indicated that this was mainly due to the contact algorithms used in ABAQUS version used then. In fact when the same simulations were run in newer Abaqus ver. 6.12, all numerical instabilities problems disappeared and we were able to successfully complete all analysis simulations until we had containment with 30 layers as previously suggested by starting from multilayered metallic fan case or by our developed analytic formula. It was effectively seen 30 layers were sufficient to contain the blade debris thus confirming our initial finding based on hybrid analysis. The results are presented in **Erreur ! Source du renvoi introuvable.18**. The remaining problem is now that as the number of layers increase the required computer time is also increased.

New Numerical Results

A parametric study was performed for assessing how the material model can be applied to an industrial problem and for assessing if predictions in terms of the number of plies needed to contain the debris and total weight reduction are in agreement with industrial observations. As a preliminary result, Figure 18 shows that as the number of plies is increased, the radial velocity decrease after impact and eventually upon radial confinement, this velocity should be zero or negative. This figure also indicates that for 30 layers, it important to account for plastic behaviour of the blade, since in the last case we have confinement while in elastic case this is not the case. Moreover, it was found in a typical industrial application, that the number of elements with acceptable mesh size is computationally prohibitive thus requiring use of high performance computers.

Figure 18 Radial velocity change in terms of number of dry Kevlar plies.

5. Conclusions

Composite or hybrid containment fan cases are in practice made from multiple layers of high performance fabrics to defeat the specific types of threats they are exposed to. Hence, as a result, a major part of the fabric target energy absorption stems from the interaction of individual layers with each other in the pack. To study such interaction existing in a real fan case, the shell crossover model is used to simulate the ballistic impact experiments on multi-ply Kevlar® 129 targets.

Numerical tests of a projectile impacting on a fabric plate were conducted and the influence of the number of plies on the final impact velocity has been studied. Also we studied the influence of various other material parameters that were input in the VUMAT to assess their influence over the results. Predicting how many plies were needed to stop the projectile based on partial simulation was a key objective of that section. It was found out that for a multilayered dry fabric flat plate it is indeed possible to predict the number of plies needed to prevent penetration and this prediction has been verified with numerical testing.

When applying the developed methodology to curved environment encountered in real industrial engine fan case, the numerical instabilities were initially encountered when more than 10 Kevlar dry fabric layers were wrapped around a metallic ring and it was not possible to terminate the simulation. An artificial recourse to a multilayered metallic structure was used and combined with successful hybrid fan case simulations to derive an analytic formula capable of predicting the number of plies required to stop the confine the debris. A theoretical predictions of 30 layers was obtained but this had to be confirmed by numerical fan blade containment simulation using a fully hybrid fan case as it was shown in this paper. Hence in contrast with our previous work [3,9] on a similar topic the new results show that with our meso-scale VUMAT model for ballistic fabric, we are now able to perform and complete all simulations for any number of layers without any numerical instabilities before termination.

The obtained results show that the model is a good one but further work is still needed to make it more robust and less computationally expensive in industrial finite element simulation context [1,2]. Hence improved meso-scale material model based on smeared shell element combined with multiscale hybrid finite elements has still to be developed so that significant impact in the designing, analyses and implementation of composite materials in aircraft structures can be expected.

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